

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14202489>

USING PROBLEM-BASED LEARNING TECHNOLOGY IN MUSIC LESSONS IN A COMPREHENSIVE SCHOOL

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Abstract: *This article examines the direction of improving the quality of training professional personnel using problem-based learning technologies when conducting classes in the humanities, and also proposes features and means of implementing the logical-heuristic method in studying the humanities.*

Key words: *“music perception”, problem-based learning method, technologization of the educational process, heuristic methods.*

The main task of musical and aesthetic education in a general education school is to form students' need for the perception of highly artistic music, to cultivate artistic taste and correctly assess the phenomena of the surrounding musical life. Communication with highly artistic music has a beneficial effect on the mental development of students, awakens their creative powers, activates imagination and fantasy.

Acquaintance with music at school is carried out through a variety of forms of musical activity of students. But whatever these forms (singing, playing musical instruments, playing music, listening), the basis of any of them is the active process of perceiving music.

In musicological, psychological, and pedagogical literature, there is no single definition of the very concept of “perception of music”. Most researchers believe that the perception of music is the unity of an emotional response and differentiated hearing of music. “... We not only feel or experience certain states, but also differentiate the perceived material, make a selection, evaluate, therefore, think,” wrote B. V. Asafiev. We find confirmation of this idea in Yu. A. Kremlev, who believes that “... a full-fledged perception of music implies intonational listening, comprehension of emotions, objects, processes reflected by music.”

The essence of the perception of a new musical work lies in the listener’s desire to feel and understand the position of the composer, to reveal the idea expressed by him, to give a social and artistic assessment of this composition in the context of the modern development of musical culture.

The listener’s interpretation of a musical work differs from the original author’s one, since the personality is always included in the social relations of its era and in social communication. The music perceived by the listener is passed through the prism of his views, ideas, emotional stereotypes, life and musical experience and, thanks to this, is transformed in his mind.

At the heart of the methodology of musical education, we see a lesson that includes four types of work that complement each other: listening to music, choral singing, movement to music and musical creativity. These types of musical activity constitute a single method that develops the process of conscious mastery of the musical language, the upbringing of the creative principle inherent in the child’s psyche.

We traditionally pay much attention to enhancing the perception of music by teenagers (problem-based learning, the widespread use of various musical creative tasks that require search and creative cognitive activity).

The necessary conditions that activate the process of musical perception include the following:

- expanding the personal listening experience of children;
- wide involvement of works of related arts to awaken students’ interest in music;

- activation of children's own activities in the process of getting acquainted with musical works through singing the main musical themes (vocalization).

With problem-based learning, all aspects of the educational process (the content of knowledge; the process of activity, which acquires a search dynamic character; the forms of organization of this activity) enhance their positive impact on the comprehensive knowledge of high school students of works of musical art. This influence is provided by a number of conditions:

- posing problems arising from the content, but based on the knowledge and experience of students;
- organizing a search based on the experience and cognitive skills of schoolchildren;
- the relationship between the search and reproductive activities of students;
- a variety of types of search educational activities.

The use of problem-based learning is especially effective in cases where the content of the educational material is aimed at the formation of concepts of knowledge about the laws of music; when it is not fundamentally new; when this content is available for independent searches of students, i.e. problem situations are in the zone of proximal development of their cognitive capabilities.

The creation of problem situations in music classes in general education classes can be ensured by setting a system of continuously complicated questions and tasks for students, the solution of which cannot be carried out by direct reproduction of educational material, but requires the establishment of new connections between phenomena.

Let us illustrate the above with a living example from the experience of pedagogical activity.

Topic of the lesson: "Genre of the piano concerto. The concept of the forms of "rondo" and "sonata allegro". The second concerto for piano and orchestra by S. V. Rachmaninov. The poetry of Russian nature in the piano work of S. V. Rachmaninov and the landscape lyrics of I. I. Levitan.

The predominant nature of the content of the educational material: theoretical, descriptive (analytical).

Ways of presenting information: verbal, visual (illustrations, audio recording).

The nature of the cognitive activity of students: reproductive-search.

Novelty of content: partial.

The degree of difficulty of the educational material: high.

Goals and objectives of training: the formation of knowledge, skills and emotional-semantic and comparative analysis of musical works, the development of musical and auditory abilities, intelligence, emotions.

Forms of education: a lesson in the assimilation of new knowledge, generalization and systematization of previously acquired knowledge, mastering the skills of analysis.

Teaching methods: lecture, conversation, problematic presentation of the material, analysis of musical works, illustrations, oral control (individual and frontal survey).

Students are familiar with the genre of piano concerto, with the concepts of the forms "sonata allegro" and "rondo" from the "Music" program, so the conversation method is used at the beginning of the lesson. The oral communication of the teacher is accompanied by questions to the students, which force the latter to actively engage in the work.

The explanation of the new material (Second Concerto for Piano and Orchestra by S. V. Rachmaninov) takes place in the form of a lecture (explanatory and illustrative presentation of the material) with practical assignments for students (analysis of fragments of the concerto), focused on the reproductive and search activities of schoolchildren. Search situations are created by the teacher through a comparative analysis of fragments of piano concertos by S. V. Rachmaninov, L. Beethoven, P. I. Tchaikovsky, previously known to students. The teacher can ask the question: "What is unusual about the concert of S. V. Rachmaninov, how does it differ from the works of this genre known to you?"

Analysis of the landscape lyrics by I. I. Levitan ("Evening. Golden Reach", "Birch Grove", "Evening Ringing", "At the Pool", "Above Eternal Peace", "March",

“Twilight”) is also built in the form of a conversation , while the attention of students is aimed at analyzing the artistic means used by the master: the compositional and color solutions of paintings, painting techniques. For example, when analyzing the paintings “Evening. Golden Reach” and “Evening Bells” students must determine and explain the difference in the moods of both paintings with one artistic image - evening nature. Analyzing the picture “At the pool”, the teacher poses the following questions to the students:

What is the mood in this picture?

- why does the viewer have a feeling of anxiety, anxiety?
- What visual media does the artist use?
- what color scheme of the image did the artist choose and why?
- with what means of musical expression can these colors be compared?

By posing a question of a problematic nature, “What, in your opinion, does the paintings of I. I. Levitan have in common with the works of S. V. Rachmaninov?” the teacher creates a search situation, for the resolution of which the students listen and independently analyze the second part of the concert. When listening, the teacher should direct the main attention of schoolchildren to understanding the timbre colors used by the composer, to the structural features and nature of the melody. At the end of the lesson, after questioning the students in a generalizing word, the teacher should sum up.

Thus, a modern music lesson is a real necessity today. It contributes to the expansion of opportunities for school education, is a conductor of the ideas of humanitarian education and aesthetic enrichment of the individual, a way to improve the quality of education. Such lessons contribute to the definition of the position of the teacher in relation to the child as cooperation, a joint interested desire to achieve high results in educational activities.

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